

The Election of the Deacons in Acts 6:1-8: An Insight for National Integration

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Abstract

Nigeria is a country inhabited by various ethnic groups of essentially dissimilar anthropologies. In a pluralistic society of this nature, peaceful co-existence and national integration are usually a herculean task. Irrespective of several attempts made by successive Nigerian governments to foster unity and create a sense of patriotism among the citizens, palpable discontentment arising from injustice, nepotism, marginalization and inequality inter-alia are common place. The feeling of some sections of the country and some ethnic groups dominating others is overt leading to reactions that sometimes cause social unrest and engender ethnic cleavages which has been a bane of national integration. Like the Nigerian state, the early church faced a problem of group identities with a certain group complaining of marginalization. The church swiftly rose to the occasion under the leadership of the apostles and nipped the problem in the bud thereby restoring peaceful co-existence, progress and the propagation of the gospel (the original mandate of the church) which would have been otherwise truncated by the crisis. This paper using the synchronic exegetical research approach juxtaposed the Nigerian situation with that of the early church in Acts 6: 1-8 and used the insight thereof to admonish Nigerian leaders to adopt the pragmatic attitude of the apostles to bring a solution to the myriads of problems facing the country so that national integration will be made realizable.

Keywords: Marginalisation, national integration, peaceful co-existence

Introduction

National integration can be said to be one of the quintessential indices for nation building and peaceful coexistence in a pluralistic society such as Nigeria. This school of thought perhaps informed the wordings of the second stanza of Nigeria's old National Anthem thus:

Oh God of creation
Grant this our one request
Help us to build a nation
Where no man is oppressed
And so with peace and plenty
Nigeria may be Blessed.

The lyrics are essentially a prayer to God Almighty for national integration and the blessings attendant with it. Whether or not this prayer has been answered is a subject of intellectual discourse. One thing that is however unequivocal is that the situation in present day Nigeria is a far cry from the lofty ideals as contained in the above anthem. The successive administrations in Nigeria are not oblivious of the fact that national integration has been a mirage and therefore approved the wordings of the first stanza of the present National Anthem which seem like a clarion call on the citizenry to rise to the occasion of the content of this Anthem thus:

Arise O compatriots
Nigeria's all obey, to serve our father land
With love and strength and faith
The labour of our heroes past
Shall never be in vain

To serve with heart and might
One nation bound in freedom
Peace and unity.

That national integration has been so elusive in Nigeria begs for serious intellectual interrogation. It is on this premise that this paper delves into the problem of national integration vis-a-vis ethnicity in Nigeria with a view to proffering solution using the lesson from the election of the deacons in Acts 6: 1-8 as an insight thereof. In doing this, the paper has been structured into further sections thus: Conceptual clarification, schism in the early church and the election of deacons (Acts 6: 1-8), the trouble with Nigeria, Analysis of Acts 6: 1-8 and its implication for national integration and conclusion.

Conceptual Clarification

National integration can be said to be the process of bringing together of people of diverse cleavages of ethnic backgrounds in a pluralistic society with divergent loyalties to the various ethnic nationalities to have a common agenda hinged on loyalty to the geographical space or country which they find themselves with a view to creating a sense of patriotism and unity in diversity as one nation. According to J. Onyekazi and E.C. Okoroafor, national integration is mainly the process of bringing the various peoples of different cultural and social background together in a given social context or polity for their collective interests and good.¹ Also according to A. Abia, national integration implies both the capacity of a government to control the territory under its jurisdiction as well as a set of popular attitudes toward the nation generally described as loyalty, allegiance, and intelligence to place national above local and parochial concerns.²

M. Weiner in his study states “national integration refers specifically to the problem of creating sense of territorial nationality which overshadows or eliminates subordinate parochial loyalties”, he stated further that it also involves the amalgamation of disparate social, economic, religious ethnic and geographic elements into a single nation state”³ National integration cannot be achieved by coercion or through a fiat but a gradual evolution of patriotism vial sustained education, justice and equity it is in this vein that S. Radhakrishna opines that “national integration cannot be made by bricks and mortar, mould and hammer, but it quietly grows in people’s mind through education.” Finally, H.A. Gani defines national integration as a “social psychological and educational process through which a feeling of unity and harmony develops in the hearts of the people and a sense of common citizenship or feeling of loyalty to the nation is fostered among them.”

Schism in the Early Church and the Election of Deacons (Acts 6: 1-8)

It is not uncommon for problems to arise in many human organizations, especially when the membership is of heterogeneous backgrounds. Thorny issues such as nepotism, favouritism, injustice and marginalization *inter-alia* usually rear their ugly heads which if not nipped in the bud could be a bane of progress and peaceful co-existence. This similar situation manifested in the early church where there arose a murmuring of the Grecian Jews against the Hebraic Jews because their widows were neglected in the daily distribution of food (Acts 6: 1b). This necessitated the apostles (the twelve disciples) to call the multitude of the disciples and said “it is not desirable that we should leave the word of God and serve tables. Therefore, brethren, look out from among you seven men of honest report, full of the Holy Spirit and wisdom, who we may designate over this business. But we will give ourselves continually to prayer and to the ministry of the word. And the saying pleased the whole multitude. Then they chose, Stephen, a man full of faith and of the Holy Spirit, and Philip, Prochorus, Nicanor, Timon, Parmenas and Nicolas a proselyte from Antioch (Acts 6: 2-5). The narrative of the election was concluded by the presentation of these seven deacons before the apostles which after they had prayed laid their hands on them which is a form of commissioning for the execution of the assignment. They dutifully carried out the task to the admiration of all thereby bringing equity and inclusiveness which engendered growth and expansion of the church.

It is worthy of note, the pro-activeness of the apostles in handling this teething problem without procrastination which otherwise would have snowballed into a myriads of problem that would have stunted the

growth of the early church. R.E. Dickson noted that if not for the managerial acumen and sagacity of the apostles in proffering solution to this problem, the church would have been in turmoil at her infancy of four to five years of her existence.⁴ The deacons were men of reputable character who were elected across the board representatives of the various interest and ethnic groups in the church. They were also devoted to their calling and merciful for it takes a merciful mind to take care of widows who are usually underdogs in the society. This view is corroborated by A. Straugh as he christens ‘deacons’ as agents of mercy whose task is to attend to the needs of people. Through the deacons, the local church’s charitable activities are effectively organized and centralised. The deacons are distributors of relief, and agents of mercy. They help the poor, the jobless, the sick, the widowed, the elderly, the homeless, the shut-in, the refugees and the disabled.⁵

Furthermore T.J. Keller in his work ‘ministries of mercy’ also portrays deacons as agents of mercy as he states that ‘mercy’ is the impulse that makes us sensitive to hurts and lacks in others and makes us desire to alleviate them for mercy has to do with man’s misery.”⁶

From the foregoing, it is evident that whoever aspires to occupy the office of a deacon should possess attributes of honesty, empathy, devotion to duty and mercy. The success recorded as a result of the activities of the deacons in the early church is perhaps the driving force behind the perpetuation of that office till date in the body of Christ. Analysis of the election of the deacons and the lessons emanating there from as an insight for national integration would be presented in the subsequent section of this paper.

The Trouble with Nigeria

According to C. Achebe in his book, *The Trouble with Nigeria*;

The trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a failure of leadership. There is nothing wrong with Nigeria land, climate, water, air or anything else. The Nigeria problem is the unwillingness and inability of its leaders to arise to the responsibility, to the challenge of personal example which is a hallmark of true leadership if other countries are affected with natural disaster, Nigeria own disaster is leadership failure.⁷

This viewpoint is a truism to the extent that the successive leaderships in Nigeria have failed to show enough political will to tackle headlong the myriad of problems facing the country. Topical issues such as ethnicity, marginalization, injustice, insecurity and sectionalism inter-alia are some of the problems that undermine the very foundation of Nigeria posing great danger to her existence. They are like an albatross threatening the unity of Nigeria as a nation by creating fertile ground for allegiance to the various ethnic nationalities that make up Nigeria instead of patriotic ideology that would lead to national integration. Indeed, it may not be a fallacy for one to argue within the ambit of current happenings that Nigeria is not yet a nation but a country made up of various ethnic nationalities tied together by a rope of sand.

It is pertinent at this juncture to highlight a few of the problems that constitute an Achilles’ heel and a bane of national integration. According to F.U. Okafor prior to 1914 when the Northern and Southern protectorates were amalgamated, the geographical space called Nigeria today was inhabited by various tribal groups, such as the Haua, Igbo, Yoruba, Tiv, Idoma, Kanuri, Efik, Ijaw etc. with distinct culture, political system, social and religious value distinct from one another.⁸ A. Eme states that the various ethnic groups in Nigeria could be estimated to be up to 310 in number and that if Nigeria should be a United Nation then these ethnic units should be wielded together and made to place loyalty to the new nation first”.⁹ As mentioned earlier, the bringing together of these numerous ethnic groupings with different cultural identities and ways of life without their consent was like a marriage of convenience occasioned by the British colonialist for their ulterior motives. It can therefore be argued that in the creation of the Nigeria state, the British paid little or no attention to the ethnic lines or cultural differences of the people. According to E.N. Onwu, “the British were more interested in exploring and exploiting the deep natural and human resources of the people for their own economic and political benefits thus; through superior firepower, they lumped together people and nations who see no reason for their common existence as members of the same society.”¹⁰ It can be inferred that the coercive fusion of different ethnic and cultural groups

into a single political economy ruptured the relative harmonious intergroup relationship that once existed among the people before colonization.

Apart from the above merger antics of the British colonialists, the way the country was structured speaks volume of their hidden agenda of 'divide and rule'. The British did appreciate that there was need to form a federal system of government as one way of bringing about integration of the new nation. Thus it saw the creation of the regions as "the beginning of the fusion of innumerable small units into three and from there into one."¹¹ The choice of the three regions created in 1945 using the instrumentality of Richard's constitution and their disproportionate sizes which were neither based on religious nor cultural homogeneity is baffling to many students of Nigerian history especially as the size of the Northern region alone was more than the sizes of Eastern and Western regions put together. E.C. Amucheazi in an attempt to explain this scenario submitted thus:

The step could be seen and was in fact seen by nationalists as a deliberate act to balkanize the country and perpetuate British rule. The fact is that the foremost nationalists then agitating for independence came from the south and the British administration felt the need to isolate and split them. Each region subsequently developed a kind of corporate identity against the others and the North against the South. Various colonial acts that tended to reinforce these dichotomies were glaring.¹²

E.C. Amucheazi stated further that the regional outlook created reinforced by the British affected even the army. Thus, the first military coup d'état in 1966 was said to be southern and sometimes Igbo led, while Lt. Col. Gowon was quoted as saying in September that "you all know that since the end of July, God in His power, has entrusted the responsibility of this great country of ours, Nigeria, to the hands of another Northerner."¹³

From the foregoing there can be a general consensus that the numerous problems of Nigeria stem from the legacy of the colonialists bequeathed to Nigeria. Having said this, it's worthwhile to consider an Idoma adage that states that "if, someone else positions you in a hunting expedition, you need to reposition yourself so that you will not be devoured by a wild dangerous animal." Perhaps, the successive administrations in Nigeria are not oblivious of these problems caused by colonial heritage and have attempted to foster national integration via various laws and creation of some institutions. Establishment of Federal Government Colleges otherwise known as Unity Schools, Federal Character Commission, quota system and indeed provisions in the constitutions for fundamental human rights etc. are a few examples. This consciousness of the importance of national integration perhaps informed the writing of the preamble of the 1999 Nigerian constitution as amended, the part of which is presented thus;

We the people of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, having firmly and solemnly resolved, to live in unity and harmony as one indivisible and indissoluble sovereign nation under God, dedicated to the promotion of inter-African solidarity, world peace, international co-operation and understand. And to provide for a constitution for the purpose of promoting the good government and welfare of all persons in our country, on the principles of freedom, equality and justice, and for the purpose of consolidating the unity of our people.¹⁴

It is clear that the fundamental principles of the constitution as highlighted in the preamble above has been a mirage and it is the view of this paper that the election of the deacons in Acts 6: 1-8 and the attendant solutions to the Schism in the early church can be replicated as an antidote to the myriads of problems of Nigeria whereby national integration can be enhanced as analysed in the following section.

Analysis of Acts 6: 1-8 and its Implication for National Integration

As presented in section two of this paper where there was a Schism in the early church as a result of marginalization, inequity in the distribution of resources and racial segregation etc. which resulted into murmuring, disunity and lack of cohesion that occasioned the intervention of the apostles whereby deacons were elected by the congregation whose duties they carried out faithfully thereby bringing an end to skirmishes and

enhanced peaceful co-existence and growth of the church. The scenario in the early church can be said to be analogous to that of Nigeria although at a macroscopic level and dimension. In Nigeria both past and present and probably in the future if urgent steps are not taken to find a solution, the problems of ethnicity, hues and cries of marginalization, injustice and lack of patriotism and underdevelopment inter alia will continue to hold sway.

The problems have become so hydra headed and the government in power today seems to have run out of ideas to proffer any solution to the extent that massive corruption, insecurity in all forms, unemployment, dwindling of national resources leading to a state of despair in the citizenry have become almost a norm. In some situations where the leadership claim to rise to the occasion, the results are not seen due to lack of political will to punish offenders and perpetrators of heinous crimes against the state to the extent that some schools of thoughts accuse government of complicity. The seeming lacklustre attitudes of Nigerian leaders are in contrast with the attitudes of the apostles (leaders) who rose to the occasion and brought about solutions to the problems of the early church.

Some salient leadership qualities of the Apostles worthy of emulation by Nigerian leaders include, honesty, pro-activeness and devolution of duties immediately the problems were made known to the apostles they were proactive and asked the congregation to freely elect deacons without them interfering with the process. This is a lesson for Nigerian leaders to learn as elections in Nigeria are usually manipulated dictated by godfathers who install people into various offices who at the end of the day must act their benefactors' scripts which definitely breeds corruption and cannot pave way for national integration. The apostles also concerned themselves with their primary duty of propagation of the gospel rather than veering into the business of serving the tables which is a clear case of devolution of duties. This principle must be imbibed and practised by Nigerian leaders in order to create a sense of belonging in the citizenry.

The election of the deacons was democratic and representative of all the interest groups and this helped a great deal in dousing the tension thereby ensuring unit and growth. This is a vital lesson for Nigeria electoral system to ensure free, fair, democratic and representative process where every section of the country is adequately represented. The deacons elected were honest, of reputable character and agents of mercy as earlier mentioned and therefore carried out their duties diligently and obtained result. Nigerian elected representatives and leaders at all levels of governance must imbibe and practice these reputable qualities of the deacons and avoid seeing political positions as avenues for amassing wealth and egocentrism. They must see themselves as servant leaders of the people and must be caring, merciful and agents of succour, development and national integration.

It may not be out of place to agree with Chinua Achebe as he postulated that the problem of Nigeria is that of leadership as he states that: "If other countries are affected with natural disaster, Nigerian own disaster is leadership failure."¹⁵ From inception, Nigeria lacked leaders with strong moral character like the apostle who had the ability to lead, inspire and motivate to rise against the challenges of ethnic and religious bias, Nigeria is plagued with primordial leaders with strong ethnic and religious sentiments and bias which have contributed in no small way to undermine the quest for national integration.¹⁶

It is not as if the successive Nigerian leaders are not aware of myriads of problems working against national integration in Nigeria but the inexplicable challenge is their palpable lack of political will to tackle these problems headlong. Like the apostles, the government of President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan took the bulls by the horns by organizing a national conference made up of the *crème de la crème* of every facet of Nigerian society in 2014 where issues of national concern and integration were frankly discussed and dialogued and far reaching recommendations were made for implementation. He was unfortunately not re-elected in 2015 and because government is a continuum, it was expected that the present government will implement the recommendations, but to the surprise of many Nigerians, the present leadership bluntly refused to attend to it for whatever reason. It is interesting to note that nagging national issues, such as revenue sharing formula, rotational political offices such as presidency, governorship etc. within the geo-political zones or the senatorial zones as the case may be with the objectives of giving a sense of belonging to every section of the country for equity were part of the agreement reached at the conference. This would have solved the age long problem of marginalization and

therefore foster unity and national integration as opposed to the perennial arrangement where leadership is lopsided in favour of setting section of the country to the detriment of others. This form of injustice and inequity cannot augur well for national integration. Freedom of worship is also embedded in constitution, but religious sentiment has never ceased to raise its ugly head in the scheme of things in Nigeria. Until our leaders become honest pragmatic and nationalistic like the apostles in formulating and implementing government policies, the quest for national integration will continue to be a mirage.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that Nigeria is blessed with natural and human resources, however, the multi-ethnic diversities are pluralism which should have been harnessed as sources of strength and national integration have unfortunately been used over the years both by the colonialists and the indigenous Nigerian leaders to disunite this country and perpetuate their ulterior agenda via divide and rule. If really the successive Nigerian leaders would imbibe the reputable characters of the apostles by creating an egalitarian society devoid of ethnic, primordial and religious sentiment, Nigeria would have been a great nation raising her head high among the committee of nations. The leaders cannot pretend to be unaware of the problems of Nigeria that have worked against national integration. There must be the political will by the leaders to crush these problems by avoiding impunity, corruption, nepotism, ethnic and religious sentiment etc. Strong institutions and not powerful individuals must be created and made to function optimally to ensure the rule of law and equity in all facets of ramification to ensure the continuity of Nigeria where all citizens will be patriotic and nationalistic rather than paying allegiance to their various ethnic nationalities. Nigeria is the only country we have and everything noble must be done like apostles did to foster unity and national integration. Leaders come and go, but Nigeria as a country remains and must be preserved for the benefits of all no matter whose ox is gourd. The common parlance in Nigeria that “soldier go, soldier come, but barrack remains” is apt.

Endnotes

¹J.C. Onyeakazi, *National Integration in Nigeria: A Philosophical Insight*,” www.research.gate-net, 3. 8/03/2019. Accessed 17/08/2022.

²V.B.E. Abia, *Government and Politics in Africa: A Comprehensive Approach*. (Lagos: BNSB, 2006), 2.

³M. Weiner, *Political Culture and Political Development* (New York: Princeton University Press, 1967), 5.

⁴R.E. Dickson, “Teachers’ Bible International, King James Version with Commentary,” *African International Missions South Africa*. (2017), 1331.

⁵A. Strauch, “*Minister of Mercy, the New Testament Deacon*” Lewis & Roth Publishers, Littleton, 2007), 156.

⁶M. Weiner, *Political Culture and Political Development* (New York: Princeton University Press, 1967), 8.

⁷C. Achebe, *The Trouble with Nigeria* (U.S.A.: Heinemann Educational Book, 1984), 1.

⁸F. U. Okafor, *New Strategies for Curbing Ethnic and Religious Conflict in Nigeria* (Enugu Forth Dimension Publishers Ltd., 1997), 5.

⁹A. Eme, “*The Teaching of Political Science in Nigeria: A Problem-Solving Approach*,” paper presentation at the Political Science Association Meeting (1979), 12.

¹⁰E.A. Onwu, Ethnicity, National and Federalism in Nigeria: An Interactive Trinity of Relationship,” *Benin Journal of Historical Studies*. (1999), 8.

¹¹J.C. Onyeakazi, *National Integration in Nigeria: A Philosophical Insight*,” www.research.gate-net 8/03/2019. (20). Accessed 17/08/2022.

¹²Ibid.

¹³Ibid., 21.

¹⁴www.vanguarding.com.>2 “The 2014 National Conference Report Must Live,” 30/09/2015. Accessed Date 17/08/2022.

¹⁵C. Achebe, *The Trouble with Nigeria* (U.S.A.: Heinemann Educational Book, 1984), 1.

¹⁶Ibid.